

DAMAGE ACCUMULATION IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES DUE TO A CONCENTRATED LOAD

Hiroshi Suemasu and Osamu Majima

*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology,
Sophia University
7-1 Kioi-cho Chiyodaku, Tokyo 102, Japan*

SUMMARY: Instability and propagation process of multiple penny-shape interlaminar delaminations in circular axi-symmetric nonlinear plates subjected to a quasi static transverse load, which is an idealized problem of damage accumulation in composite laminates due to low velocity impact loading, is numerically studied through a finite element analysis. A fracture element proposed to simulate the crack propagation is modified for elements with mid-node. The condition for crack propagation is also changed to make the convergence of the solution with element size more smooth. Both failures due to maximum stress and fracture mechanical instability are possible to be considered by using the present element. The element is applied to a problem of a penny shape crack propagation in an infinite body. The results converge smoothly to the theoretically predicted solution with a quite rough element division. Then, the element is used to simulate the propagation of multiple delaminations in a laminate, where nonlinearity due to finite deflection is considered. The early stages of the damage propagation depend on the initial delamination size. When the plate size used in CAI test standard is considered, the effect of the nonlinearity is not significant for ordinary composite laminates except plates of very high interlaminar toughness. The finite element results are consistent with the failure process inferred from the energy release rate distribution theoretically obtained in the precedent studies[5].

KEYWORDS : Plate, Delaminations, Impact, Energy release rate, Finite element analysis, Finite displacement

INTRODUCTION

Structures made of composite laminates, particularly made of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP), are susceptible to impact damage such as transverse cracking, delamination etc. Design loads of the structures are often limited by the degraded compressive performance due to damage•[for example 1-3]. Special emphasis is placed on the interlaminar delaminations below the impact point, which usually occur in the form of multiple delaminations. The mechanism of damage accumulation due to impact load must be well understood in order to utilize CFRP laminated structures to their full advantage. The damage accumulation process in linear and nonlinear circular plate has been studied theoretically by the authors[4,5] and the mechanism of the evolution of the multiple delaminations is well explained. However, in order to incorporate dynamic effect, it is necessary to use numerical procedure which can handle the crack propagation. Many workers studied the failure process based on the damage mechanics[for example, 6,7]. Sankar et al.[8] studied dynamic delamination propagation in the cantilever beam based on the fracture mechanics by finite element analysis. Liu et al.[9] and Razi et al.[10] investigated a delamination growth induced by a spherical indenter where growth of the

delamination was judged by using energy release rate. Though a crack propagation can be predicted fracture mechanically by using the energy release rate at the crack tip region, the energy which should be absorbed along the crack surface during crack growth cannot be considered.

In the previous paper [11], a numerical method was proposed to simulate the delamination propagation by introducing a special fracture element, which consider the energy consumed at the crack surface. With the use of the fracture element, many interesting results were obtained, while extremely fine mesh was required to obtain converged solution. It is quite tough condition to apply the method in the dynamic analysis because an enormous computation time is expected. In the present paper, the element is improved to apply the element with mid nodes. The condition for the crack propagation is modified to improve the convergence of the solution.

2. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSYS

• A finite element analysis is proposed which can simulate crack propagation process in the composite laminates subjected to not only static but also dynamic load. A package finite element program (MARC) is used for the present research, because this program has user subroutine to program elements with arbitrary load-deformation history can be defined. To use the element the planes where the delamination will propagate can be presumed beforehand. In order to well simulate failure process including the case of dynamic loading, a fracture element which is set at the interlaminar area should have the following features.

- The element fails when the stress reaches its strength and/or the energy release rate exceeds a critical value.
- The element has no or negligibly small reaction force once it fails. The contact problem must be considered on the cracked surface.
- The energy stored in the element will not be returned back to the system when it fails. The energy may be equal to that necessary for the crack propagation, that is, fracture toughness of the material.

In order to realize a fracture element which satisfy the above conditions, a nonlinear spring element in conjunction with a user subroutine program is used. This idea is thought to be equivalent to Dugdale-Barenblatt's fracture model. Let us consider x_n and x_s coordinate system as shown in Fig.1, which are normal and parallel to the crack plane. Double nodes are placed at the expected plane of the crack propagation. The spring elements of no length connect the double nodes in the respective directions. In the figure, only the spring in the normal direction is drawn for conciseness of the figure. The spring elements connecting the nodes of two normal elements above and below the crack plane are assumed to be a unit interlaminar area. So, the two corner nodes are connected by two fracture elements because the node is common for the neighboring elements. When the expansion of one of the springs exceeds a critical value, the interlaminar area is determined to be broken and all the springs are cut. The nonlinear traction working between the double nodes is determined from the interlaminar material properties, that is, strength and toughness and the traction force is assumed to be proportional to the power form of the relative displacement. The failure process was not sensitive to the nonlinear properties as long as the energy stored in the spring until its failure is same. Before failure the relationships between the traction forces F_{ni} and F_{si} in x_n and x_s directions and relative displacements Δu_{ni} , Δu_{si} at each

Fig.1: Schematic illustration of the fracture elements in the finite element modeling.

fracture (interlaminar nonlinear spring) element are defined as

$$F_{ni} = \begin{cases} p_i k_c \Delta u_n & (\Delta u_n < 0) \\ p_i k_t (\Delta u_n)^\alpha & (0 \leq \Delta u_n < \Delta u_{nc}) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{si} = \pm p_i k_s |\Delta u_s|^\beta \quad (|\Delta u_s| < \Delta u_{sc}) \quad (2)$$

where the parameters k_t , k_s , Δu_{nc} and Δu_{sc} can be determined from the maximum stress and interlaminar toughness of the material when α and β are presumed. The coefficient p_i is a factor to be multiplied according to the position of the spring element.

When 4-node rectangular element is used, this value is 1/2. For 8-node isoparametric element the factor of 1/6 is chosen for the corner node and 4/6 for mid-node. As $k_c \Delta u_n$ is a resistant force during compression, a large positive value should be chosen for the spring constant k_c in order to prevent the material from overlapping. The strengths of the present fracture elements in tension and shear F_{nc} and F_{sc} are determined from the interlaminar strengths σ_c and τ_c .

$$F_{nc} = k_t (\Delta u_{nc})^\alpha = \sigma_c A, \quad F_{sc} = k_s (\Delta u_{sc})^\beta = \tau_c A \quad (3)$$

where A is the area of the element. The energy stored in the element until the failure of the element is assumed to be equal to the fracture toughness.

$$\int_0^{\Delta u_{nc}} k_t x^\alpha dx = AG_{Ic} , \quad \int_0^{\Delta u_{sc}} k_s x^\beta dx = AG_{IIc} \quad (4)$$

Then, the parameters of the fracture elements k_t , k_s , Δu_{nc} and Δu_{sc} are determined from equations (3) and (4);

$$\Delta u_{nc} = \frac{(\alpha + 1)G_{Ic}}{\sigma_c}, \quad \Delta u_{sc} = \frac{(\beta + 1)G_{IIc}}{\tau_c} \quad (5)$$

$$k_t = \frac{\sigma_c^{\alpha+1} A}{\{(\alpha + 1)G_{Ic}\}^\alpha}, \quad k_s = \frac{\tau_c^{\beta+1} A}{\{(\beta + 1)G_{IIc}\}^\beta} \quad (6)$$

Once the relative displacement Δu_n or Δu_s exceeds critical relative displacement Δu_{nc} or Δu_{sc} in a spring, the material is thought to be failed and the resistance both in tension and shear of all the fracture elements between the two elements above and below the crack are set zero hereafter.

$$F_n = \begin{cases} k_c \Delta u_n & (\Delta u_n < 0) \\ 0 & (\Delta u_n > 0) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$F_s = 0 \quad (8)$$

Frictionless contact is assumed here for simplicity. Some frictional effect can be incorporated by introducing a inplane force proportional to the compressive pressure at the delaminated surface.

4. PROPAGATION OF CIRCULAR CRACK IN A INFINITE HOMOGENEOUS BODY

An evolution process of a circular crack in a homogeneous infinite body shown in Fig.2 is analyzed using the fracture element defined in the preceding section. The problem has an exact solution when the material is linear elastic. The crack propagation is stable since the energy release rate decreases with the crack propagation under constant load. As the problem is axisymmetric, 4 node and 8-node axisymmetric solid element are used. A typical finite element mesh is illustrated in Fig.3. Only half of the model is analyzed owing to the symmetry. Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, strength and fracture toughness of the model are 100 *GPa*, 0.3, 400 *MPa* and 1 *kJ/m²*, respectively. An initial crack radius is 2 *mm*. To avoid a singularity at the loading point, a uniform distributed load is applied at a small circular portion of a radius of 1 *mm*

Fig.2 A circular crack in an infinite body. A uniform distributed load is applied at the center portion of the crack surface.

Fig.3: A typical finite element mesh of a cracked body. The element size is same along the surface where crack is expected to propagate.

instead of a concentrated load. As the stress field is pure mode I, the fracture element is set only in normal direction. The nonlinear parameter α is set 0.1.

The convergence of the solution with respect to the element size is studied and relationships between the applied load and the crack radius are plotted in Fig.4 with a theoretically obtained ideal relationship. The converged solution need not coincide with the theoretical result, since

Fig.4: Relationships between the applied force and crack radius when uniformly distributed load is applied at a center of the crack. The crack radii quickly approach an asymptotic value with the decrease of the element size in both cases of 4 node element and 8 node element.

some expansion of the fracture elements is allowed in the finite element analysis. Present method of modeling the interlaminar portion makes the convergence very quick with the element size compared to the former modeling [12]. The stiffness of the spring element just at the crack tip portion is halved for the case of 4-node element and made 1/6 times smaller for the case of the 8-node element. The difficulty in convergence in the former modeling may be due to the modeling the distributed resistance at the crack tip area by concentrated spring and the present modeling may relaxes the problem by introducing compliant spring at the crack tip node. We can use 8 times wider element owing to the present improvement.

5. PROPAGATION OF DELAMINATIONS IN TRANSVERSELY ISOTROPIC CIRCULAR LAMINATES

The present fracture element was applied to problems accompanying delamination growth in transversely isotropic linear and nonlinear circular laminates fixed at its edge. The material constants are listed in Table 1. A transverse displacement of the top surface of the center element was increased gradually. A typical finite element mesh is illustrated in Fig.5. The model was divided into elements of same width in a radial direction where crack propagation was expected. The solution was obtained by an iteration method.

Fig.5: A typical finite element mesh of a delaminated plate

Table 1: Material properties of transversely isotropic plate

$E_x = E_y$	56.5 GPa
ν_{xy}	0.316
E_z	9.15 GPa
$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$	0.262
$G_{xz} = G_{yz}$	4.18 GPa
σ_c	32.6 MPa
τ_c	85.0 MPa
G_{Ic}	200 J/m ²

First, the behavior of plates with a circular delamination of an initial radius of 2 mm was

calculated by using 4 node and 8-node elements. Only the relationships between the load and the delamination radius obtained by the use of the 8 node element is plotted in Fig.6. Comparing with the results obtained by using former fracture element (the element size must be smaller than 0.0625 mm [12]), notable improvement of the convergence property with element size was obtained for both 4 node and 8 node element. The delamination started to grow at a slightly lower

Fig.6: Delamination propagation in a quasi-isotropic laminate.

load than the approximate solution based on the classical plate theory [4,5]. The necessary force for the delamination propagation gradually increased with the size of the delamination and asymptotically approached to the approximate solution. This is due to the effect of the stress concentration at the loading point. The load obtained is plotted against center displacement of lower surface of the plate in Fig.7. The zigzag path above 3 kN was caused by the finite crack extension. The secant modulus decreased with the load due to the delamination crack propagation

Fig.7: A relationship between load and center displacement for a laminate with a center delamination

and the load approached to an approximate solution.

Next, the behavior of the nonlinear plates with three delaminations was studied. The damage accumulation processes are plotted in Fig.8 for the plates with the initial delamination sizes of 1 mm and 2 mm. The results for the initial delaminations of 2 mm are plotted with hollow symbols and those for the initial delaminations of 1 mm with solid symbols. When the radius of the initial delaminations is 1 mm, the delamination near the impacted surface, delamination 1, started to propagate at 1.8 kN and stably propagated with load. Then, at the load of 2.4 kN, the center delamination, delamination No.2, started to propagate. Both delaminations No.1 and 2 stably

Fig.8: Effect of the size of initial delaminations on initial stage of damage accumulation for the laminate with three delaminations

expanded with the load increase. The growth of No.2 delamination was faster than No.1 delamination. At the load of 2.6 kN the delamination No.3 suddenly propagated unstably by 2 mm. In this moment both delaminations of No.1 and No.2 also propagated unstably by some amount. Finally the radii of all the delaminations became identical and all three delaminations stably propagated with slight increase of the load. In the case of initial delamination of 1 mm, the results looked different. The delamination No.1 started to propagate at a lower load of 1.4 kN. When the radius of the delamination exceeded 2 mm, the load level was a little higher than the case of 2 mm. The delamination No.2 did not grow until 2.75 kN and then propagated unstably by 2.5 mm. Then, the two delaminations grew stably until load reached 3.4 kN. The delamination No.2 was longer than delamination No.1. The delamination No.3 started to unstably propagate by 8.5 mm at the load. The load level was higher than the necessary load expected from the theoretical solution based on the plate theory [5]. The rest of delaminations also propagated by 4 and 3 mm. A notable decrease of the load was observed during this unstable propagation of the delaminations. Then, all the delamination propagated stably with the load. The result hereafter almost coincided with that of the case of 2 mm as expected. When the delamination of small radius was near the back surface, the delamination was thought to be difficult to propagate owing to the three dimensional stress distributions.

The applied load is plotted against the center displacement of the back surface of the plate in Fig.9. Only slight decrease of the stiffness was found when No.1 delaminations started to propagate. A notable reduction of the stiffness was observed when the delamination No.2 started to propagate. There was a sudden drop of the load due to large unstable delamination propagation when No.3 delamination became unstable. The load increased hereafter due to the geometrical instability. The delaminations of course grew with the increase of the center displacement. The relationship between the load and the center displacement agreed well with the curve inferred from the theoretically obtained approximate solution.

6. SUMMARY

A fracture element proposed in the previous paper [12] was modified and applied to a problem of instability of a crack in an infinite body first and the solution obtained agreed well with the results inferred from a theory. The solution was found to quickly converge to a value with decrease of element size. Then, the element was utilized to solve problems that one and multiple delamination cracks in nonlinear plate grew in a circular plate subjected to a transverse load. When multiple delaminations were solved, this program could well simulate even when unstable crack propagation accompanies. The initial damage accumulation process could depend on the size of initial damage. The effect of the nonlinearity may not be significant when the size of the plate assigned by the CAI test standard is tested except the case of very interlaminar toughness. The present element may be applicable to the various problems accompanying the crack propagation for both static and dynamic cases.

Fig.9: Relationships between the applied load and center displacement for the laminate with three delaminations. The initial delamination radii are mm.

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